

On the Relation between Peptisation of a Precipitate and its Electrokinetic Potential.

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The phenomenon of peptisation is in a general way opposite to the process of coagulation and any theory that would attempt an explanation of the process of peptisation, should in more sense than one, be the reverse of the process of coagulation. An explanation on this basis was put forward by Freundlich ("Colloid and Capillary Chemistry," 1926, p. 472). Now recent researches on the cataphoretic velocity of colloidal particles in presence of electrolytes have generally shown (Mukherjee, Chaudhury and Bhabak, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 13, 370; Mukherjee, Chaudhury and Sen-Gupta, *ibid.*, 1936, 13, 421) that the rate of cataphoresis often increases as coagulation proceeds and that high cataphoretic speeds of colloids are usually observed at coagulating concentrations of electrolytes. These are facts that go against coagulation taking place at a low critical constant potential and as such the prevalent views regarding the phenomenon of coagulation require to be changed and it suggests that current views regarding peptisation may also require to be modified.

Buzagh (*Kolloid Z.*, 1929, 48, 33; 1927, 41, 169) working with suspensions of charcoal and ferric hydroxide found that for a definite concentration of a peptising electrolyte, the cataphoretic velocity increases to a maximum with increasing mass of the peptised substance and afterwards diminishes. Investigations were also carried out by Kruyt and van der Willigen (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1928, 139, 53) who tried to extend the earlier considerations of Fajans (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1921, 97, 478) and Mukherjee and his co-workers (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 3, 335; 1927, 4, 459). They observed that the electrokinetic potential of different substances can be increased by all kinds of electrolytes, but only those ions, which fit into the lattice of the particles, can peptise the substance (*cf.* also the work of Cysouw, mentioned by Verwey, *Chem. Rev.*, 1935, 16, 363.) Before any explanation of these results can be advanced from the electrokinetic or the ion adsorption point of view it appears that the experiments on the general nature of the variations of the cataphoretic velocity of a precipitate during the course of its peptisation would throw

considerable light on causes at work in such phenomena and on the mechanism of peptisation.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The systems studied are ferrocyanides and sulphides of a number of metals. In the case of the ferrocyanides of zinc, copper and uranium, no special peptising agents were used. The ferrocyanides were precipitated as follows :

I. The ferrocyanide solution A (0.1 N) is added to the other salt solution B (0.1 N)

- (i) in equal volumes of 100 c.c. each ;
- (ii) with 1 c.c. excess of A ; 101 c.c. of A and 100 c.c. of B ;
- (iii) with 1 c.c. excess of B ; 100 c.c. of A and 101 c.c. of B.

II. Solution B (0.1 N) is added to the ferrocyanide solution A (0.1 N).

- (i) in equal volumes of 100 c.c. each ;
- (ii) with 1 c.c. excess of A ; 100 c.c. of B and 101 c.c. of A ;
- (iii) with 1 c.c. excess of B ; 101 c.c. of B and 100 c.c. of A.

The salts used for the precipitation of the respective ferrocyanides are (1) $\text{CuSO}_4, 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$; (2) $\text{UO}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2, 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, (3) $\text{ZnSO}_4, 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6, 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Thus the precipitate of each ferrocyanide was obtained in six different ways. The mixtures were centrifuged and the precipitates thrown down. The supernatant liquids were decanted off, 200 c.c. of fresh conductivity water were added to the precipitate and the contents thoroughly mixed by stirring. The cataphoretic velocities of the precipitates initially formed as well as of the particles suspended in fresh conductivity water after each washing were measured with the microcataphoretic apparatus described before (*cf.* Mukherjee, Chaudhury, and Bhabak, *loc. cit.*; Mukherjee, Chaudhury and Sen-Gupta, *loc. cit.*). The results are given in Figs. 1, 3, and 4. 0.01 N-potassium ferrocyanide and 0.01 N-copper sulphate were also used. Since the amount of the precipitate was small, the wash liquid used each time was 100 c.c. The results are given in Fig. 2.

The sulphides were precipitated by passing hydrogen sulphide through solutions of their respective salts acidified with hydrochloric acid. The precipitates were washed by decantation with conductivity

FIG. 1.

Curve 1— $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ added to $CuSO_4$ in equal vol.

2— $CuSO_4$ added to $K_4Fe(CN)_6$, latter in excess.

3— $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ added to $CuSO_4$, former in excess.

4— $CuSO_4$ added to $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ in equal vol.

5— $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ added to $CuSO_4$, latter in excess.

6— $CuSO_4$ added to $K_4Fe(CN)_6$, former in excess.

FIG. 2.

Curves 1-4 refer to CuSO_4 added to $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ in equal vol., CuSO_4 in excess, equal vol, and $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ in excess respectively.

FIG. 3.

No. of washings.

- Curve 1— $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ added to $UO_2(NO_3)_2$, former in excess
 2— $UO_2(NO_3)_2$ „ $K_4Fe(CN)_6$, latter in excess
 3— $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ „ $UO_2(NO_3)_2$ in equal vol.
 4— $UO_2(NO_3)_2$ „ $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ in „ „
 5— $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ „ $UO_2(NO_3)_2$, latter in excess
 6— $UO_2(NO_3)_2$ „ $K_4Fe(CN)_6$, former in excess.

FIG. 4.

No. of washings.

Curves 1—3 refer respectively to $ZnSO_4$ added to $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ with $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ in excess; in equal vols.; $ZnSO_4$ in excess. Curves 4—6 refer respectively to $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ added to $ZnSO_4$ (4)—in equal vols.; $ZnSO_4$ in excess; $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ in excess.

water and the c.v. again measured. Then hydrogen sulphide was passed through the solution and the c.v. measured again. Table I contains the results obtained.

TABLE I.

C. v. of the sulphide precipitates.

Substance	* $V \times 10^5$		
	Just after precipitation.	After washing.	After passing H_2S .
1. As_2S_3	32.5 (N)	22.9 (N)	31.1 (P)
2. SnS_2	43.7 "	35.2 "	42.5 "
3. Sb_2S_3	23.2 "	20.9 "	38.2 "
4. HgS	29.6 "	27.6 "	39.3 "
5. CdS	14.7 "	12.4 "	28.0 "

(N) No peptisation.

(P) Peptisation.

DISCUSSION.

Relation between Electrokinetic Potential and Peptisation.

Results of different ferrocyanides (*cf.* Figs. 1 to 4) show that the cataphoretic velocity generally increases with the peptisation of a precipitate under all the above conditions of precipitation. The initial c.v. of the precipitate obtained, the nature of the variation of the c.v. of the precipitate before it peptises into a colloidal solution and the final c.v. of the colloid formed from the precipitate, however, depend on the conditions of precipitation.

The following observations require to be elucidated :—

(i) When 0.1N- $CuSO_4$ and 0.1N- $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ are the precipitants, the initial charge is always positive but with the centinormal solutions as precipitants, the initial charge is always negative.

(ii) The initial charge of the uranium ferrocyanide precipitate is always positive. Decinormal solutions were used for precipitation.

* The charge is always negative and is expressed in cm. per sec. per volt/cm.

(iii) The initial charge of zinc ferrocyanide is always negative.

(iv) The course of variation of the c.v. on repeated washings till peptisation takes place (*i.e.*, till the precipitate passes into a finer state of subdivision).

It has been suggested in earlier papers (*loc. cit.*) that the observed high cataphoretic speed at the coagulating concentrations of electrolytes is the result of aggregation. The phenomenon of coagulation consists of two processes, (i) agglomeration of the primary colloidal particles and (ii) the settling of the particles. The commencement of the first process may be easily explained by assuming that just after the addition of an electrolyte, the density of the charge on the colloid diminishes and this diminution helps aggregation of the colloidal particles. With aggregation, the cataphoretic velocity becomes higher and higher. Further agglomeration at this high density of charge requires to be explained. It might be assumed (*cf.* Freundlich, "Colloid and Capillary Chemistry," 1926, p. 434) that the larger particles act as nuclei, where particles of smaller size condense for the larger particles have got larger spheres of action. Or in the alternative it might also be assumed that with the irregular growth of the clusters of particles, charges on the so-called growing aggregates are accumulated at particular spots on the surface and further growth of the particles takes place with attachment of smaller particles at those places on the surface where the density of charge is either nil or very low.

After the particles have grown to a certain size, they are not affected any more by the brownian movement of the particles and due to the action of gravity they settle down and this explains the second part of the progress of coagulation. The final equilibrium is attained when no further aggregation occurs with time, and the latter particles already settled down acquire a low charge due to the adsorption of the oppositely charged ions (*cf.* Mukherjee, Chaudhury and Bhabak, *loc. cit.*). If the views on coagulation as set forth above be true, then the process of peptisation by washing with the solvent alone can be looked at in the case of ferrocyanide precipitates in the following way:—

By washing with the solvent, the electrolytes are removed and the density of charge tends to be high. (This, however, is not always the case as will be evident from the *initial* parts of some curves in Figs. 1 to 4 depending, of course, on the nature of the precipitate studied.)

As a result of this high density of charge of the individual small particles within the agglomerate, the agglomerate breaks up and we get particles of smaller size with high density of charge (cf., the steepness of the curves in all the figures, when it passes from the precipitate to the sol condition).

At this stage, small particles are subjected to the action of brownian movements and they are, therefore, suspended in the medium and further agglomeration is prevented due to the existence of this high density of charge of the particles formed.

In the case of sulphides (cf. Table I), the increment of charge with peptisation after passing hydrogen sulphide is easy to follow from the point of view developed above. *The initial decrease of the charge of the precipitate after washing is, however, explicable by assuming that HS-ions primarily adsorbed on the surface are removed by washing.*

SUMMARY.

1. The electrokinetic potential of the particles of a precipitate increases during peptisation.
2. A polar precipitate does not always show the same sign of charge as that of the constituent ion present in excess at the time of precipitation. The charge appears also to depend on the concentrations of the precipitants taken.

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